

Supporting Information

Small atom doping: A (synergistic) strategy to reduce Sn_{Zn} recombination center concentration in $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4$?

Alex Jimenez-Arguijo^{1,2}, Alejandro Navarro Güell², Yudania Sanchez¹, Claudia Malerba³, Matteo Valentini³, Pascal Becker⁴, Leo Choubrac⁴, Thomas Unold⁴, Zacharie Jehl Li-Kao², Sergio Giraldo², Edgardo Saucedo²*

A. Jimenez-Arguijo, Y. Sanchez

Catalonia Institute for Energy Research (IREC), Sant Adrià del Besòs, 08930, Barcelona, Spain

A. Jimenez-Arguijo, A.N. Güell, Z. Jehl, S. Giraldo, E. Saucedo

Photovoltaic Group, Electronic Engineering Department, Polytechnic University of Catalonia (UPC), 08034, Barcelona, Spain

C. Malerba, M. Valentini

Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development (ENEA), Casaccia Research Center, 00123, Roma, Italy

P. Becker, L. Choubrac, T. Unold

Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin für Materialien und Energie GmbH, Department Structure and Dynamics of Energy Materials, 14109, Berlin, Germany

E-mail: ajimenez@irec.cat

Table S1. Cation ratios of the metallic precursor and CZTSe samples.

Hydride mass (mg)	Precursor/CZTSe (Thermal Process)	Cu/(Zn+Sn)	Zn/Sn	Cu/Zn	Cu/Sn
0	Precursor (1S)	0.71±0.01	0.99±0.01	1.42±0.01	1.40±0.02
5	Precursor (1S)	0.70±0.01	1.03±0.01	1.38±0.01	1.42±0.02
10	Precursor (1S)	0.68±0.01	1.02±0.01	1.35±0.01	1.38±0.01
20	Precursor (1S)	0.70±0.01	1.03±0.01	1.37±0.01	1.41±0.01
0	Precursor (2S)	0.70±0.01	1.04±0.01	1.37±0.02	1.43±0.02
5	Precursor (2S)	0.69±0.01	1.04±0.01	1.36±0.02	1.42±0.02
10	Precursor (2S)	0.68±0.01	1.02±0.01	1.34±0.01	1.36±0.01
20	Precursor (2S)	0.70±0.01	1.03±0.01	1.37±0.02	1.14±0.02
0	CZTSe (1S)	0.70±0.03	1.09±0.07	1.34±0.05	1.46±0.07
5	CZTSe (1S)	0.71±0.01	1.10±0.02	1.35±0.03	1.49±0.03
10	CZTSe (1S)	0.70±0.01	1.13±0.03	1.31±0.02	1.49±0.04
20	CZTSe (1S)	0.70±0.01	1.10±0.02	1.34±0.02	1.47±0.02
0	CZTSe (2S)	0.69±0.01	1.09±0.02	1.33±0.02	1.45±0.02
5	CZTSe (2S)	0.71±0.01	1.13±0.03	1.33±0.01	1.50±0.04
10	CZTSe (2S)	0.70±0.01	1.14±0.02	1.32±0.02	1.50±0.03
20	CZTSe (2S)	0.70±0.01	1.12±0.03	1.33±0.02	1.50±0.04

Figure S1. a) Temperature profiles used in this work b) Se/cation ratio of the different samples, effects of both temperature profile and hydride mass are observed. 1-step processes show a higher selenium content with LiAlH₄ mass while 2-step show the opposite trend. Notice the enhancement on the selenization homogeneity for the 1-step processes.

Figure S2. SEM cross-section images of 2-step processes: a) reference sample, and b) 20 mg LiAlH₄ sample. Grain size is reduced with the increased LiAlH₄ mass, as opposed to 1-step process. Excessive exposure to alkali, Al, H or the low pressure step might be responsible for this degradation in the layer morphology.

Figure S3. a) Optoelectronic parameters of samples with different mass of LiAlH_4 . 21 different sub-cells were measured in each sample, the averages and standard deviations are presented. b) Illuminated J-V curves of the best sub-cell of each sample.

Figure S4. EQE ratios for the best cell of 1-step annealed samples with LiAlH_4 over the reference best cell.

Figure S5. Raman spectra of the bare absorber, zoom in different spectral regions. a) A-type defect spectral region, $[\text{V}_{\text{Cu}}+\text{Zn}_{\text{Cu}}]$. b) B-type defect spectral region, $[\text{Zn}_{\text{Cu}}+\text{Zn}_{\text{Sn}}]$.

Figure S6. Dark J-V curves of the best 1-step set samples. Notice the reduction in recombination current J_0 .

SCAPS-1D numerical analysis details

In order to simplify the model, and as a direct consequence of no reliable methods to extract the material properties of the as-grown MoSe₂ layer, it is not included in the simulation. Instead, an ideal (flat band) contact is assumed. This should not drastically change the simulation outcomes, since very few electron-hole pairs are generated at the back-contact side of the 1.5-micron absorber. ^[1]

Material	Back Contact	p-CZTSe	n-CdS	i-ZnO	n-ZnO	Front Contact
Thickness (μm)	-	1.5	0.06	0.05	0.4	-
Band Gap (eV)	-	1.04	2.5	3.3	3.4	-
Electron Affinity (eV)	5.14	4.3	4.2	4.4	4.4	4.25
Dielectric Permittivity (relative)	-	8.5	10	9	9	-
CB effective density of states (cm^{-3})	-	$2.2 \cdot 10^{18}$	$1.3 \cdot 10^{18}$	$2.2 \cdot 10^{18}$	$2.2 \cdot 10^{18}$	-
VB effective density of states (cm^{-3})	-	$1.8 \cdot 10^{19}$	$9.3 \cdot 10^{18}$	$1.8 \cdot 10^{19}$	$1.8 \cdot 10^{19}$	-
Electron thermal velocity (cm/s)	-	10^7	$3.1 \cdot 10^7$	10^7	10^7	-
Hole thermal velocity (cm/s)	-	10^7	$1.6 \cdot 10^7$	10^7	10^7	-
Electron Mobility ($\text{cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{s}$)	-	Variable (20-40)	160	50	100	-
Hole Mobility ($\text{cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{s}$)	-	40	15	5	25	-
Shallow Uniform donor density	-	-	10^{17}	$5 \cdot 10^{17}$	$5 \cdot 10^{20}$	-
Shallow Uniform acceptor density (cm^{-3})	-	$2 \cdot 10^{16}/$ $8 \cdot 10^{16}$	-	-	-	-
Absorption Coefficient ($1/\text{cm}\cdot\text{eV}^{1/2}$)	-	$1.25 \cdot 10^5$	$5 \cdot 10^5$	From File	From File	-
Radiative Recombination coefficient (cm^3/s)	-	$1.04 \cdot 10^{-10}$	-	-	-	-

The defect implemented in CZTSe is based on literature parameters given by Ref [13], the defect concentration has been used to parametrize the lifetime (60 ps to 260 ps

correspond to $1.8 \cdot 10^{16}$ and $4.1 \cdot 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ respectively). The fact that hole mobility in CdS is low is in order to not have a photovoltaic contribution of CdS in the simulation, to be consistent with the experiment. The thickness of CZTSe and CdS has been extracted from SEM microscopy. The band gap of CZTSe has been extracted from EQE. Shallow acceptor density has been extracted from an estimation of the minimum of the C-V profile. The contact work functions have been chosen to obtain flat bands, thus considering an ohmic junction. Shunt and series resistances of the cell have been implemented in the simulation parameters.

Defect	Concentration	Type	Energetic Distribution	Et (eV above VB)	Electron Capture Cross Section (cm^2)	Hole Capture Cross Section (cm^2)	Surface recombination velocity (cm/s)
p-CZTSe (Sn_{Zn})	$4.1 \cdot 10^{15} / 1.8 \cdot 10^{16}$ (60/260 ps)	Neutral	Single	0.5	$9.3 \cdot 10^{-14}$	$9.3 \cdot 10^{-14}$	-
Electric contacts	-	-	-	-	-	-	10^7

The experimental reflectivity was included in the right contact for a more accurate current approximation.

Defect reactions with small atom doping

The possible effects of the presence of small atom are discussed using the literature data, and it is identified that H_i and Li_{Cu} are the lowest formation energy defects.^{[2], [3]} These defects can donate electrons to the conduction band of CZTSe, increasing E_F :

- (1) $\text{H}_2\text{Se} \rightarrow 2\text{H} + \text{Se} \rightarrow 2\text{H}_i^+ + 2e^- + \text{Se}$
- (2) $\text{Li-Se} + \text{V}_{\text{Cu}}^- \rightarrow \text{Li} + \text{Se} + \text{V}_{\text{Cu}}^- \rightarrow \text{Li}_{\text{Cu}} + e^- + \text{Se}$

Note that the presence of Cu vacancies is expected for Cu-poor conditions and the low formation energy of this defect. Nevertheless, the formation energy of Li_{Cu} is lower. The increased E_F (or e^- concentration) demands that the formation energy of other donor defects is increased while the formation energy of acceptor defects should be reduced.^{[4], [5]} Therefore, Zn vacancies should be occupied by Cu and Li (forming Cu_{Zn} and Li_{Zn} acceptor defects) which reduce the overall energy of the system.

- (3) $\text{Li-Se} + \text{V}_{\text{Zn}}^{2-} \rightarrow \text{Li}_{\text{Zn}}^- + e^- + \text{Se}$
- (4) $\text{Cu}_{\text{Cu}} + \text{V}_{\text{Zn}}^{2-} \rightarrow \text{Cu}_{\text{Zn}}^- + \text{V}_{\text{Cu}}^-$

The reduction of Sn_{Zn} defects is a consequence of the combined presence of H and Li donor defects, added to the steric suppression of Sn_{Zn} due to Li_{Zn} presence. The low formation energy of donor Cu_{Zn} and Li_{Zn} requires that it is also formed in e^- rich conditions. Thus, the low formation energy of Cu_{Zn} and Li_{Zn} limits the increase in $[e^-]$ and E_F :

- (5) $\text{Li-Se} + \text{Zn}_{\text{Zn}} + e^- \rightarrow \text{Li}_{\text{Zn}}^- + \text{Zn} + \text{Se}$
- (6) $\text{Cu}_{\text{Cu}} + \text{Zn}_{\text{Zn}} \rightarrow \text{Cu}_{\text{Zn}}^- + \text{Zn}_{\text{Cu}}^+$

The suppression of Sn_{Zn} is a consequence of the free e^- donated by H and Li:

- (7) $\text{Sn-Se} + \text{V}_{\text{Zn}}^{2-} \leftarrow \text{Sn}_{\text{Zn}}^{2+} + 4e^- + \text{Se}$
- (8) $\text{Sn-Se} + \text{Zn}_{\text{Zn}} \leftarrow \text{Sn}_{\text{Zn}}^{2+} + \text{Zn} + 2e^- + \text{Se}$
- (9) $\text{Sn-Se} + \text{Li}_{\text{Zn}}^- \leftarrow \text{Sn}_{\text{Zn}}^{2+} + \text{Li} + e^- + \text{Se}$

Also, the reduced concentration of Zn vacancies, which are occupied by Cu and Li under high E_F (H and Li presence) conditions further suppresses reaction (7).

References

- [1] S. Giraldo *et al.*, “Rear interface engineering of kesterite $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4$ solar cells by adding CuGaSe_2 thin layers,” *Prog. Photovoltaics Res. Appl.*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 334–343, 2021, doi: 10.1002/pip.3366.
- [2] K. Otte, G. Lippold, H. Neumann, and A. Schindler, “Hydrogen in CuInSe_2 ,” *J. Phys. Chem. Solids*, vol. 64, no. 9–10, pp. 1641–1647, 2003, doi: 10.1016/S0022-3697(03)00100-8.
- [3] M. He *et al.*, “High Efficiency $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSn}(\text{S},\text{Se})_4$ Solar Cells with Shallow LiZn Acceptor Defects Enabled by Solution-Based Li Post-Deposition Treatment,” *Adv. Energy Mater.*, vol. 11, no. 13, pp. 2–9, 2021, doi: 10.1002/aenm.202003783.
- [4] S. Kim, J. A. Márquez, T. Unold, and A. Walsh, “Upper limit to the photovoltaic efficiency of imperfect crystals from first principles,” *Energy Environ. Sci.*, vol. 13, no. 5, pp. 1481–1491, 2020, doi: 10.1039/d0ee00291g.
- [5] W. Chen, D. Dahliah, G. M. Rignanese, and G. Hautier, “Origin of the low conversion efficiency in $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnS}_4$ kesterite solar cells: The actual role of cation disorder,” *Energy Environ. Sci.*, vol. 14, no. 6, pp. 3567–3578, 2021, doi: 10.1039/d1ee00260k.